

Mapping Study Survey

Introduction

Mapping the availability of services for adults with cerebral palsy; a pilot study

The aim of this survey is to map available services for people with cerebral palsy who are aged 18 years and older. Before we share the survey widely, we want a small number of people to complete it in order to see if it is easy to complete and if we get the information we need from it.

We are looking for adults with cerebral palsy, family members of adults with cerebral palsy, and people who provide services to adults with cerebral palsy to complete the survey. You must be 18 years or older to complete the survey. Your response will help us to create a list of existing services and to improve the survey so that we can share it more widely.

We want to know about any health service for people with CP aged 18 years and above in your area or that you are aware of. For this study, a health service includes any medical service (e.g, rehabilitation specialist, paediatrician), therapy service (e.g. physiotherapist, occupational therapist), social work service, diagnostic service, assistive technology service, support service (e.g. personal assistance, respite), disability service, charity, exercise group, accessible gym or pool, or support group that treats or supports adults with cerebral palsy.

This survey is part of the Ignition study, which aims to improve the process of transitioning from children's to adults' services for young people with cerebral palsy in Ireland. More details about the Ignition study and this survey, including an information leaflet can be found on our website (<https://www.ignitionstudy.com/mapping-services>)

The survey is anonymous and confidential. Completion of the survey indicates that you consent to take part. You can decide to stop completing the survey at any time; the answers you provide will not be recorded unless you submit the survey by pressing finish. This study is funded by the Health Research Board and has ethical approval from RCSI's Research Ethics Committee.

Please answer the following questions to help us map available services for adults with cerebral palsy in Ireland. The survey should take no longer than 5 minutes to complete.

To complete the survey please click [Next](#)

Are you a...? (Please choose whichever describes you best) * *Required*

- Adult with cerebral palsy
- A parent or guardian of an adult with cerebral palsy
- Other family member of an adult with cerebral palsy
- Partner of an adult with cerebral palsy
- Personal assistant
- Neurologist
- Paediatrician
- Orthopaedic surgeon
- Social worker
- Psychiatrist
- Clinical psychologist
- Physiotherapist
- Occupational therapist
- Manager
- GP
- Speech and language therapist
- Nurse
- Dietician
- Researcher or academic
- Administrator
- Other

If you selected Other, please specify:

Following the previous question, please select if any of the following roles also apply to you *Optional*

- Adult with cerebral palsy
- A parent or guardian of an adult with cerebral palsy
- Other family member of an adult with cerebral palsy
- Partner of an adult with cerebral palsy
- Personal assistant
- Paediatrician
- Neurologist
- Orthopaedic surgeon
- Social worker
- Psychiatrist
- Clinical psychologist
- Physiotherapist
- Occupational therapist
- Manager
- GP
- Speech and language therapist
- Nurse
- Dietician
- Researcher or academic
- Administrator
- Other

If you selected Other, please specify:

Which region of Ireland are you based in? If you work with people with cerebral palsy,

please choose the region of your workplace. (tick all that apply) * *Required*

- Carlow
- Cavan
- Clare
- Cork
- Donegal
- Dublin
- Galway
- Kerry
- Kildare
- Kilkenny
- Laois
- Leitrim
- Limerick
- Longford
- Louth
- Mayo
- Meath
- Monaghan
- Offaly
- Roscommon
- Sligo
- Tipperary
- Waterford
- Westmeath
- Wexford
- Wicklow
- Prefer not to say

Are you primarily?

- A service provider (e.g. a paediatrician, a physiotherapist, a social worker)
- A service user (e.g. a person with CP or a family member of a person with CP)?

Service Provider

Which of the following sector(s) do you work in? (tick all that apply)

- Academia or research
- HSE
- Private sector
- Voluntary sector
- Other

If you selected Other, please specify:

If applicable, which CHO(s) do you work in? (tick all that apply)

- CHO 1: Donegal, Sligo/Leitrim/West Cavan, and Cavan/Monaghan
- CHO 2: Galway, Roscommon, Mayo
- CHO 3 :Clare, Limerick, and North Tipperary/East Limerick
- CHO 4: Kerry, North Cork, North Lee, South Lee, and West Cork
- CHO 5: South Tipperary, Carlow/Kilkenny, Waterford, and Wexford
- CHO 6:Wicklow, Dun Laoghaire, and Dublin South East
- CHO 7:Kildare/West Wicklow, Dublin West, Dublin South City, and Dublin South West
- CHO 8 : Laois/Offaly, Longford/Westmeath, Louth, and Meath
- CHO 9 :Dublin North, Dublin North Central, and Dublin North West
- Not applicable
- I don't know
- Prefer not to say

Service 1

Please provide as many details as you can about the health service or services you know for people with cerebral palsy aged 18 years and older

A health service may include:

- A medical service (e.g. rehabilitation specialist, a paediatrician)
- A therapy service (e.g. physiotherapist, occupational therapist, speech and language therapist)
- A social work service
- A diagnostic service
- An assistive technology service
- A support service (e.g. personal assistance, respite)
- A charity or support group that treats or supports adults with cerebral palsy
- An exercise group that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy
- A gym or pool that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy

Name of Organisation

Name of Service (e.g. adult physiotherapy service, specialist seating service, assistive technology service)

Location. (Please describe in as much detail as possible eg. name of centre, address,

town, city)

Website link to service

Other identifying information

Have you or someone you know (aged 18+) received assessment, treatment, or support at this service for their cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No

Is the service delivered through public or private healthcare?

- Public
- Private
- I don't know

Do you believe this service has expertise in treating or supporting adults with cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Do you know of any more services?

- Yes
- No

Service 2

Please provide as many details as you can about the health service or services you know for people with cerebral palsy aged 18 years and older

A health service may include:

- A medical service (e.g. rehabilitation specialist, a paediatrician)
- A therapy service (e.g. physiotherapist, occupational therapist, speech and language therapist)
- A social work service
- A diagnostic service
- An assistive technology service
- A support service (e.g. personal assistance, respite)
- A charity or support group that treats or supports adults with cerebral palsy
- An exercise group that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy
- A gym or pool that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy

Name of Organisation

Name of Service (e.g. adult physiotherapy service, specialist seating service, assistive technology service)

Location (Please describe in as much detail as possible eg. name of centre, address,

town, city)

Website link to service

Other identifying information

Have you or someone you know (aged 18+) received assessment, treatment, or support at this service for their cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No

Is the service delivered through public or private healthcare?

- Public
- Private
- I don't know

Do you believe this service has expertise in treating or supporting adults with cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Do you know of any more services?

- Yes
- No

Service 3

Please provide as many details as you can about the health service or services you know for people with cerebral palsy aged 18 years and older

A health service may include:

- A medical service (e.g. rehabilitation specialist, a paediatrician)
- A therapy service (e.g. physiotherapist, occupational therapist, speech and language therapist)
- A social work service
- A diagnostic service
- An assistive technology service
- A support service (e.g. personal assistance, respite)
- A charity or support group that treats or supports adults with cerebral palsy
- An exercise group that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy
- A gym or pool that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy

Name of Organisation

Name of Service (e.g. adult physiotherapy service, specialist seating service, assistive technology service)

Location (Please describe in as much detail as possible eg. name of centre, address,

town, city)

Website link to service

Other identifying information

Have you or someone you know (aged 18+) received assessment, treatment, or support at this service for their cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No

Is the service delivered through public or private healthcare?

- Public
- Private
- I don't know

Do you believe this service has expertise in treating or supporting adults with cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Do you know of any more services?

- Yes
- No

Service 4

Please provide as many details as you can about the health service or services you know for people with cerebral palsy aged 18 years and older

A health service may include:

- A medical service (e.g. rehabilitation specialist, a paediatrician)
- A therapy service (e.g. physiotherapist, occupational therapist, speech and language therapist)
- A social work service
- A diagnostic service
- An assistive technology service
- A support service (e.g. personal assistance, respite)
- A charity or support group that treats or supports adults with cerebral palsy
- An exercise group that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy
- A gym or pool that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy

Name of Organisation

Name of Service (e.g. adult physiotherapy service, specialist seating service, assistive technology service)

Location (Please describe in as much detail as possible eg. name of centre, address,

town, city)

Website link to service

Other identifying information

Have you or someone you know (aged 18+) received assessment, treatment, or support at this service for their cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No

Is the service delivered through public or private healthcare?

- Public
- Private
- I don't know

Do you believe this service has expertise in treating or supporting adults with cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Do you know of any more services?

- Yes
- No

Service 5

Please provide as many details as you can about the health service or services you know for people with cerebral palsy aged 18 years and older

A health service may include:

- A medical service (e.g. rehabilitation specialist, a paediatrician)
- A therapy service (e.g. physiotherapist, occupational therapist, speech and language therapist)
- A social work service
- A diagnostic service
- An assistive technology service
- A support service (e.g. personal assistance, respite)
- A charity or support group that treats or supports adults with cerebral palsy
- An exercise group that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy
- A gym or pool that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy

Name of Organisation

Name of Service (e.g. adult physiotherapy service, specialist seating service, assistive technology service)

Location (Please describe in as much detail as possible eg. name of centre, address,

town, city)

Website link to service

Other identifying information

Have you or someone you know (aged 18+) received assessment, treatment, or support at this service for their cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No

Is the service delivered through public or private healthcare?

- Public
- Private
- I don't know

Do you believe this service has expertise in treating or supporting adults with cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Do you know of any more services?

- Yes
- No

Service 6

Please provide as many details as you can about the health service or services you know for people with cerebral palsy aged 18 years and older

A health service may include:

- A medical service (e.g. rehabilitation specialist, a paediatrician)
- A therapy service (e.g. physiotherapist, occupational therapist, speech and language therapist)
- A social work service
- A diagnostic service
- An assistive technology service
- A support service (e.g. personal assistance, respite)
- A charity or support group that treats or supports adults with cerebral palsy
- An exercise group that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy
- A gym or pool that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy

Name of Organisation

Name of Service (e.g. adult physiotherapy service, specialist seating service, assistive technology service)

Location (Please describe in as much detail as possible eg. name of centre, address,

town, city)

Website link to service

Other identifying information

Have you or someone you know (aged 18+) received assessment, treatment, or support at this service for their cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No

Is the service delivered through public or private healthcare?

- Public
- Private
- I don't know

Do you believe this service has expertise in treating or supporting adults with cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Do you know of any more services?

- Yes
- No

Service 7

Please provide as many details as you can about the health service or services you know for people with cerebral palsy aged 18 years and older

A health service may include:

- A medical service (e.g. rehabilitation specialist, a paediatrician)
- A therapy service (e.g. physiotherapist, occupational therapist, speech and language therapist)
- A social work service
- A diagnostic service
- An assistive technology service
- A support service (e.g. personal assistance, respite)
- A charity or support group that treats or supports adults with cerebral palsy
- An exercise group that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy
- A gym or pool that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy

Name of Organisation

Name of Service (e.g. adult physiotherapy service, specialist seating service, assistive technology service)

Location (Please describe in as much detail as possible eg. name of centre, address,

town, city)

Website link to service

Other identifying information

Have you or someone you know (aged 18+) received assessment, treatment, or support at this service for their cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No

Is the service delivered through public or private healthcare?

- Public
- Private
- I don't know

Do you believe this service has expertise in treating or supporting adults with cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Do you know of any more services?

- Yes
- No

Service 8

Please provide as many details as you can about the health service or services you know for people with cerebral palsy aged 18 years and older

A health service may include:

- A medical service (e.g. rehabilitation specialist, a paediatrician)
- A therapy service (e.g. physiotherapist, occupational therapist, speech and language therapist)
- A social work service
- A diagnostic service
- An assistive technology service
- A support service (e.g. personal assistance, respite)
- A charity or support group that treats or supports adults with cerebral palsy
- An exercise group that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy
- A gym or pool that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy

Name of Organisation

Name of Service (e.g. adult physiotherapy service, specialist seating service, assistive technology service)

Location (Please describe in as much detail as possible eg. name of centre, address,

town, city)

Website link to service

Other identifying information

Have you or someone you know (aged 18+) received assessment, treatment, or support at this service for their cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No

Is the service delivered through public or private healthcare?

- Public
- Private
- I don't know

Do you believe this service has expertise in treating or supporting adults with cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Do you know of any more services?

- Yes
- No

Service 9

Please provide as many details as you can about the health service or services you know for people with cerebral palsy aged 18 years and older

A health service may include:

- A medical service (e.g. rehabilitation specialist, a paediatrician)
- A therapy service (e.g. physiotherapist, occupational therapist, speech and language therapist)
- A social work service
- A diagnostic service
- An assistive technology service
- A support service (e.g. personal assistance, respite)
- A charity or support group that treats or supports adults with cerebral palsy
- An exercise group that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy
- A gym or pool that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy

Name of Organisation

Name of Service (e.g. adult physiotherapy service, specialist seating service, assistive technology service)

Location (Please describe in as much detail as possible eg. name of centre, address,

town, city)

Website link to service

Other identifying information

Have you or someone you know (aged 18+) received assessment, treatment, or support at this service for their cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No

Is the service delivered through public or private healthcare?

- Public
- Private
- I don't know

Do you believe this service has expertise in treating or supporting adults with cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Do you know of any more services?

- Yes
- No

Service 10

Please provide as many details as you can about the health service or services you know for people with cerebral palsy aged 18 years and older

A health service may include:

- A medical service (e.g. rehabilitation specialist, a paediatrician)
- A therapy service (e.g. physiotherapist, occupational therapist, speech and language therapist)
- A social work service
- A diagnostic service
- An assistive technology service
- A support service (e.g. personal assistance, respite)
- A charity or support group that treats or supports adults with cerebral palsy
- An exercise group that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy
- A gym or pool that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy

Name of Organisation

Name of Service (e.g. adult physiotherapy service, specialist seating service, assistive technology service)

Location (Please describe in as much detail as possible eg. name of centre, address,

town, city)

Website link to service

Other identifying information

Have you or someone you know (aged 18+) received assessment, treatment, or support at this service for their cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No

Is the service delivered through public or private healthcare?

- Public
- Private
- I don't know

Do you believe this service has expertise in treating or supporting adults with cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Do you know of any more services?

- Yes
- No

Service 11

Please provide as many details as you can about the health service or services you know for people with cerebral palsy aged 18 years and older

A health service may include:

- A medical service (e.g. rehabilitation specialist, a paediatrician)
- A therapy service (e.g. physiotherapist, occupational therapist, speech and language therapist)
- A social work service
- A diagnostic service
- An assistive technology service
- A support service (e.g. personal assistance, respite)
- A charity or support group that treats or supports adults with cerebral palsy
- An exercise group that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy
- A gym or pool that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy

Name of Organisation

Name of Service (e.g. adult physiotherapy service, specialist seating service, assistive technology service)

Location (Please describe in as much detail as possible eg. name of centre, address,

town, city)

Website link to service

Other identifying information

Have you or someone you know (aged 18+) received assessment, treatment, or support at this service for their cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No

Is the service delivered through public or private healthcare?

- Public
- Private
- I don't know

Do you believe this service has expertise in treating or supporting adults with cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Do you know of any more services?

- Yes
- No

Service 12

Please provide as many details as you can about the health service or services you know for people with cerebral palsy aged 18 years and older

A health service may include:

- A medical service (e.g. rehabilitation specialist, a paediatrician)
- A therapy service (e.g. physiotherapist, occupational therapist, speech and language therapist)
- A social work service
- A diagnostic service
- An assistive technology service
- A support service (e.g. personal assistance, respite)
- A charity or support group that treats or supports adults with cerebral palsy
- An exercise group that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy
- A gym or pool that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy

Name of Organisation

Name of Service (e.g. adult physiotherapy service, specialist seating service, assistive technology service)

Location (Please describe in as much detail as possible eg. name of centre, address,

town, city)

Website link to service

Other identifying information

Have you or someone you know (aged 18+) received assessment, treatment, or support at this service for their cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No

Is the service delivered through public or private healthcare?

- Public
- Private
- I don't know

Do you believe this service has expertise in treating or supporting adults with cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Do you know of any more services?

- Yes
- No

Service 13

Please provide as many details as you can about the health service or services you know for people with cerebral palsy aged 18 years and older

A health service may include:

- A medical service (e.g. rehabilitation specialist, a paediatrician)
- A therapy service (e.g. physiotherapist, occupational therapist, speech and language therapist)
- A social work service
- A diagnostic service
- An assistive technology service
- A support service (e.g. personal assistance, respite)
- A charity or support group that treats or supports adults with cerebral palsy
- An exercise group that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy
- A gym or pool that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy

Name of Organisation

Name of Service (e.g. adult physiotherapy service, specialist seating service, assistive technology service)

Location (Please describe in as much detail as possible eg. name of centre, address,

town, city)

Website link to service

Other identifying information

Have you or someone you know (aged 18+) received assessment, treatment, or support at this service for their cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No

Is the service delivered through public or private healthcare?

- Public
- Private
- I don't know

Do you believe this service has expertise in treating or supporting adults with cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Do you know of any more services?

- Yes
- No

Service 14

Please provide as many details as you can about the health service or services you know for people with cerebral palsy aged 18 years and older

A health service may include:

- A medical service (e.g. rehabilitation specialist, a paediatrician)
- A therapy service (e.g. physiotherapist, occupational therapist, speech and language therapist)
- A social work service
- A diagnostic service
- An assistive technology service
- A support service (e.g. personal assistance, respite)
- A charity or support group that treats or supports adults with cerebral palsy
- An exercise group that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy
- A gym or pool that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy

Name of Organisation

Name of Service (e.g. adult physiotherapy service, specialist seating service, assistive technology service)

Location (Please describe in as much detail as possible eg. name of centre, address,

town, city)

Website link to service

Other identifying information

Have you or someone you know (aged 18+) received assessment, treatment, or support at this service for their cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No

Is the service delivered through public or private healthcare?

- Public
- Private
- I don't know

Do you believe this service has expertise in treating or supporting adults with cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Do you know of any more services?

- Yes
- No

Service 15

Please provide as many details as you can about the health service or services you know for people with cerebral palsy aged 18 years and older

A health service may include:

- A medical service (e.g. rehabilitation specialist, a paediatrician)
- A therapy service (e.g. physiotherapist, occupational therapist, speech and language therapist)
- A social work service
- A diagnostic service
- An assistive technology service
- A support service (e.g. personal assistance, respite)
- A charity or support group that treats or supports adults with cerebral palsy
- An exercise group that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy
- A gym or pool that is accessible to people with cerebral palsy

Name of Organisation

Name of Service (e.g. adult physiotherapy service, specialist seating service, assistive technology service)

Location (Please describe in as much detail as possible eg. name of centre, address,

town, city)

Website link to service

Other identifying information

Have you or someone you know (aged 18+) received assessment, treatment, or support at this service for their cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No

Is the service delivered through public or private healthcare?

- Public
- Private
- I don't know

Do you believe this service has expertise in treating or supporting adults with cerebral palsy?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Do you know of any more services?

- Yes
- No

Other

If you would like to add anything to your answers, please comment below. Please do not include any details that would make you identifiable

Final page

Thank You !

We will share the findings of this project on our website in early 2022.

If you would like to provide feedback for this survey please follow this link

(note this feedback will remain anonymous)

<https://brunel.onlinesurveys.ac.uk/mapping-study-feedback-survey>
